

SYMPTOMS OF PATIENTS IN THE FIRST HOURS AFTER THE ONSET OF ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME**Coropceanu I.,***Student,**Faculty of General Medicine**"Nicolae Testemitanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy**Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Grib L.***University professor,**head of the cardiology department of the "Nicolae Testemitanu"**State University of Medicine and Pharmacy**Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Abstract**

The study involves the evaluation and determination of patient's symptoms that appear in the first hours after the onset of acute coronary syndrome with the aim of raising the level of health culture that is the basis of the primary prevention of cardiovascular diseases. The research was conducted on a group of 100 patients diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction with ST-segment elevation, acute myocardial infarction without ST-segment elevation and unstable angina pectoris.

Keywords: acute coronary syndrome, acute myocardial infarction with ST-segment elevation, acute myocardial infarction without ST-segment elevation, unstable angina pectoris.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases are the pathologies with the highest risk of mortality, reaching 7.5 million deaths annually. Worldwide, ischemic heart disease ranks first in this category, with 1.8 million deaths annually. In the European countries the incidence reaches between 43-144 per 100.000 inhabitants per year [2, 3, 8, 9].

The symptoms preceding the onset of acute coronary syndrome (ACS) are the main trigger for patients who request emergency services. Recent studies demonstrate that typical symptoms in female patients are more predictive of an ACS event compared to male patients [4, 6].

According to studies, the most common reason for referral to the emergency department and hospitalization in case of ACS is chest pain [1].

At the same time, the age of patients has a particular importance in the appearance of symptoms in case of ACS, being also an important predictor of mortality, given the fact that approximately 80% of all deaths following an episode of ACS occur in individuals over 65 years of age. According to the studies carried out, it is stated that patients older than 65 years may have associated symptoms and not just the presence of the pain syndrome. Therefore, it is very important to know and identify the symptoms of patients with ACS from the multitude of associated symptoms, as quickly as possible [5, 7].

The continuous increase in the number of population suffering from cardiovascular pathologies is largely due to the indifference towards one's own health and primary prevention.

The medical education of patients regarding the responsibility for their own health constitutes one of the extra-medical functions of the medical staff. It is necessary that early intervention and preventive checks dominate the causes of referrals to doctors. Prevention instead of treatment must be cultivated in the patient's consciousness [10].

Materials and methods

The study was conducted on a group of 100 patients including 30 patients with ST-segment elevation acute myocardial infarction (STEMI), non-ST-segment elevation acute myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) and unstable angina pectoris (API). Of these patients, the onset symptoms of ACS were analyzed, including: precordial pain, dyspnea, pain in the neck and mandible region, as well as palpitations.

Results

The patients included in the study are aged between 40-89 years, being divided into 5 groups. The first group is represented by patients aged 40-49 (8%), of which 5% patients with STEMI, 1% – with NSTEMI and 2% – with API. In the group of patients aged 50-59 years (18%), the highest rate is represented by patients with API (7%), followed by NSTEMI (6%) and STEMI (5%). The group with the largest number of registered patients is the one in the 60-69 age range (38%) where 15% are patients with API, 13% – with NSTEMI and 10% – with STEMI. The group of patients aged 70-79 years (21%) recorded STEMI in 7% cases, NSTEMI in 4% and API in 10%. The last group of 80-89 years (15%) recorded the highest value in patients with NSTEMI and API (6%), then STEMI (3%).

Fig. 1. Distribution of ACS patients according to age group.

According to the analyzed data, the onset of ACS was predominantly anginal type in 92 cases, and asthmatic type in 8 cases. In the 92 cases, patients with STEMI were included - in 29%, patients with NSTEMI - in 26% and patients with API - in 37% of cases. And the asthmatic type was detected with the lowest value of 1% in the case of STEMI patients, 3% – with API and 4% – with NSTEMI.

Fig. 2. Type of onset of ACS.

Early detection of ACS symptoms is vital. The symptoms encountered in the patients during the study were: precordial pain in 92% of cases, dyspnea - in

62%, palpitations - in 18%, pain in the neck and mandibular region - in 6%, syncope - in 1%, respectively.

Fig. 3. The presence of symptoms on patients with ACS.

Precordial pain as the predominant symptom was recorded in 30% of patients with STEMI, 25% – with NSTEMI and 37% – with API. Dyspnea was highest in patients with API (30%), NSTEMI (19%) and STEMI (13%). Pain in the neck and mandibular region was

found equally in patients with STEMI and NSTEMI (3%). Palpitations were present in patients with API (14%) and NSTEMI (4%). Syncope was present in only 1% of patients with NSTEMI.

Fig. 4. Distribution of symptoms according to the diagnosis of ACS.

References

1. Among patients with ACS, the most common symptom is retrosternal pain. Thus, in the study we evaluated which type of onset is most frequently registered in patients with ACS, this being the anginal type (92%). In the case of patients with STEMI, they presented 29%, with NSTEMI – 26% and with API – 37% cases.
2. In the case of patients with ACS, the present symptoms are of major importance and very useful in detecting the pathology and formulating the diagnosis. The predominant symptoms present in patients with ACS were chest pain (92%) and dyspnea (62%). Precordial pain with the highest rate was present in patients with API (37%), STEMI (30%) and NSTEMI (25%),

and dyspnea had the highest values in patients with API (30%), NSTEMI (19%) and STEMI (13%).

3. The highest mortality rate is for patients over 65 years of age. Patients with the highest risk of an ACS episode were those aged 60-69 years (38%), followed by the group of patients aged 70-79 years (21%).

Reviewer

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